

Fast Track Report – REDMANE

DevOps/SysAdmin

Intake 14, Summer 2026

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Context

What is REDMANE?

Conceptually

“REDMANE tracks files across organisations like a catalogue tracks books across libraries”

It is inspired by problems encountered in Project Grandiose ([slide 4](#)), which is a:

- Multi-organisational research with 9 labs across 5 countries
- Multi-omics research with 13 datasets and 5 data types

Main problem: how to handle research data management at such scale? (It was a struggle: they relied on emails)

REDMANE aims to be lightweight and flexible across different research/data types. This is achieved by storing only the **metadata** of the underlying research data files in REDMANE’s Data Registry and pointing to their respective storage locations, **instead of** storing the actual research data files (as research data can be very big, e.g. gigabytes per file).

Library analogy	REDMANE	Notes
Books	Files	A library stores & tracks books, a medical research organisation stores & tracks research data files
Physical libraries	Organisations	Libraries collect, store, and track books, medical research organisations collect, store, and track data
Catalogue	Data Registry	A catalogue tracks books and their storage locations across libraries, but to read the book, you need to borrow a physical copy. REDMANE tracks data files’ metadata across organisations, but to read the data, you need to the organisation’s computer/machine.
Author’s website about a book	Data Portal	Place to display visualisation of the book. In the case of research: visualisation of summarised data.

Practically

REDMANE is an **ecosystem/environment** that consists of **(1) a data registry, (2) data portals VM** (“app store”), and **(3) mock/pretend organisations**.

This ecosystem aims to prove the concept of “metadata registry” instead of “cloud storage”.

While in this stage of REDMANE there are only 2 organisations and 2 data portals, conceptually, more organisations and data portals can be added to the environment in the future.

For more context, see slides 5-7, 11, 13, and 16-22 from [Introduction to REDMANE](#).

Devops/Sysadmin Team’s Scope in the Architecture

From the graph above, Devops/Sysadmin team works on the **data registry and data portal VMs**.

The team’s responsibilities include:

- Deployment and version control: optimise code change and deployment workflows by using Git

- Containerisation: ensure that all builds are containerised using Docker for build consistency
- SSL: ensure that connections to the Data Registry and the Data Portals are always using HTTPS (by obtaining & maintaining SSL certificates)
- Data Portals set up:
 - Add real data volume to cBioPortal
 - Set up Omero with a real working functionality
- Single Sign-On set up: achieve SSO capabilities among Data Registry, cBioPortal, and Omero.

Content

SSH

SSH key is a cryptographic authentication mechanism used to securely access remote systems over the **SSH (Secure Shell)** protocol, consisting of a **public key**, stored on the remote server, and a **private key**, which remains securely on your local machine.

SSH keys use asymmetric encryption algorithms such as RSA, ECDSA, or Ed25519. SSH keys are resistant to brute-force attacks and are not transmitted over the network during login. For more information and setup notes → [Technical Diaries](#)

SSL Certificates

SSL is a security protocol that encrypts web traffic to protect data between browsers and servers.

In our system, SSL certificates:

- Enable **secure HTTPS connections** to all public domains.
- Are issued and automatically renewed using **Certbot** with **Let's Encrypt**.
- Are stored in **persistent Docker volumes** so certificates remain valid even if containers restart.
- Are managed by **Nginx**, which decrypts HTTPS traffic before proxying it to backend services like **cBioPortal** and **OMERO**.

To better understand how SSL certificates work, see this guide (5–10 mins reading):

- [cBioPortal](#)
- [OMERO](#)

Nginx

Nginx is a lightweight web server and reverse proxy server. In our system, it primarily:

1. Acts as a reverse proxy to forward incoming requests to backend services (e.g., Keycloak, data portals).
2. Hosts and serves static HTML content.

To better understand how it works, it is recommended to run Nginx on your local machine first (follow [these steps](#) - 10 mins reading). This will help you become familiar with Docker containers and basic Nginx configuration before working in the production environment.

Certbot

Certbot is an automated tool for obtaining and renewing SSL/TLS certificates from Let's Encrypt. What we did:

- Installed Certbot directly on the VM to understand and verify its workflow → see the [tech diary](#) for details (estimated reading time: 5 mins).
- Configured Certbot to work alongside Nginx (Docker container) → see the [tech diary](#) for setup details (estimated reading time: 15 mins).

Notes:

- SSL certificates are generated and stored on the VM.
- Certificates are mounted into the Nginx container for HTTPS.
- This setup keeps certificate management at the VM level while Nginx handles secure connections.

Docker

Docker packages all REDMANE services into containers for consistent deployment across Nectar Cloud VMs.

In our system, Docker:

- Runs key services: **https-portal, Data Registry backend & database, cBioPortal, Omero**
- Uses **Docker Compose** for multi-container orchestration on Data Portals VM.
- Stores SSL certs, databases, and data in **persistent volumes** (survives container restarts).

For Docker basics (5 min read): [What is Docker? | Docker Docs](#)

Https-Portal

Https-Portal is a ready-to-use Docker image that combines the functionality of

1. Nginx: reverse proxying, hosting static frontend files, SSL termination
2. Certbot: automated SSL certificate obtainment and renewal/management

Into 1 container.

It is preferred for REDMANE because this combination makes the Docker setup for REDMANE lighter. For more context, visit: <https://github.com/SteveLTN/https-portal>

Single Sign-On (SSO)

Background

A goal for REDMANE is having a SSO feature among Data Registry, cBioPortal, and Omero.

Keycloak

Keycloak is the central authentication service (Identity Provider) in our system. It integrates with OIDC-enabled applications (e.g., cBioPortal), external identity providers (e.g., AAF), and OpenLDAP as the authoritative user directory.

For detailed architecture and component interactions → see [Keycloak Overview](#) (20 mins reading).

LDAP

LDAP (Lightweight Directory Access Protocol) is a directory service protocol used for centralised authentication, authorisation, user/group management, and identity lookup.

- In OMERO, LDAP is used to authenticate users: when a user logs in via OMERO.web or OMERO.insight, OMERO queries the LDAP server to validate credentials, creating or mapping internal OMERO accounts as configured.
- In REDMANE however, Keycloak acts as the Identity Provider, with LDAP serving as a downstream directory; the idea is for Keycloak to try to synchronize user attributes, and in **Import Users/Writable Edit Mode** settings- technically create new users in LDAP when accounts are added through the Admin Console or Account Console. [Keycloak LDAP User Federation Docs](#)
- [LDAP Authentication with OMERO](#) - This covers practical steps for deploying an OpenLDAP container via Docker, creating users within it, and explains relevant configuration parameters, as well as comparing ApacheDS and OpenLDAP for OMERO. A ready-to-use example integrating OMERO with LDAP (using Docker and ApacheDS) is available in **OME GitHub Repo: [docker-example-omero-ldap](#)**.

How Everything Fits Together

You need **SSH** to connect to the Data Registry and Data Portal VMs to make code changes and deploy new code.

When a user visits the Data Registry or a Data Portal through their browser, the request first hits **https-portal**, which terminates the HTTPS connection and forwards the request to the appropriate backend service.

On the Data Registry VM, this means routing to the FastAPI backend when requested, which processes API requests and interacts with the PostgreSQL database that stores the metadata of participating organisations' data files.

On the Data Portal VM, **https-portal** does the same HTTPS connection termination with the addition of domain-based routing to either the cBioPortal or Omero website.

All of these services are packaged as **Docker** containers and orchestrated via **Docker Compose**, ensuring consistent and reproducible deployments across the Nectar Cloud VMs.

As a next step, a **Single Sign-On (SSO)** feature needs to be set up: **Keycloak** acts as the central Identity Provider, enabling users to authenticate once and access the Data Registry, cBioPortal, and Omero without repeated logins.

The Data Registry and cBioPortal connect to Keycloak directly via **OIDC** as registered callback endpoints, while Omero requires Keycloak to be integrated with **OpenLDAP** as an Identity Provider (IdP), as the community (free) version of Omero authenticates through the LDAP protocol.

Appendix

Important Links

Name
REDMANE Interns Readme
Short Introduction to REDMANE
Long Introduction to REDMANE
Devops/Sysadmin Intake 14 (Summer 2026) Technical Diary Folder
Instructions for working on code changes & deploying codes to Data Registry VM
Intake 14's Internship Landing Page
Internship FAQs

Data Registry VM Directory Structure and Their Repos:

```
REDMANE/
├── docker-compose.yaml           # Main orchestration file
├── redmane_fastapi.dockerfile    # Backend container build
├── redmane_reactjs.dockerfile    # Frontend multi-stage build
├── data-registry.wehi-rcp.cloud.edu.au.conf.erb # Custom nginx config for path-based routing
├── .dockerignore                # Excludes unnecessary files from Docker build context
├── .gitignore                   # Excludes files/folders that may cause conflict when cloning
├── README.md
├── LICENSE
├── REDMANE_fastapi/             # Backend requirements and data
│   ├── app/
│   └── data/
│       └── REDMANE_fastapi_public_data/ # Database schemas, initialisation script
│           ...
├── REDMANE_react.js/           # Frontend requirements and codes
└── backups/                    # VM's own backups, not tracked in git
```

- Gray (REDMANE_Docker): https://github.com/WEHI-RCPStudentInternship/REDMANE_Docker.git
- Blue (Data Registry Backend/Fastapi): https://github.com/WEHI-RCPStudentInternship/REDMANE_fastapi.git
- Green (Data Registry Database): https://github.com/WEHI-RCPStudentInternship/REDMANE_fastapi_public_data.git
- Pink (Data Registry Frontend/React.js): https://github.com/WEHI-RCPStudentInternship/REDMANE_react.js.git